

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF USING LOCAL LANDRACES/VARIETIES OF FOOD PLANTS IN THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MOUNTAIN AREA

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Abstract

Romania faces a number of challenges related to food crises and food security, accentuated by the Covid-19 pandemic and the ongoing conflict in Ukraine. These challenges are particularly acute in mountain areas, which are also affected by environmental, economic and social problems. In this context, the promotion and use of local traditional plant varieties/crop landraces can help address some of these challenges by improving the productivity and resilience of farming systems, enhancing food security, promoting economic development and supporting sustainable and resilient development in mountain areas. This is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the European Parliament's motion for a resolution on addressing food security in developing countries. Preserving and promoting local populations is important for maintaining biodiversity, supporting local food systems and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. The potential benefits of using local populations in mountain areas in Romania include adaptability to local conditions, resistance to environmental changes, diseases and pests (bioaggressors), biodiversity conservation and nutritional, economic and cultural values of agro-food products. Given Romania's rich agricultural tradition and numerous local plant and food crop populations, this paper discusses how their conservation, promotion and use can contribute to supporting sustainable and resilient development in mountain areas, with specific examples of local populations in Romania.

Keywords: crop landraces; food plants; sustainable development; food security; biodiversity conservation; mountain area.

INTRODUCTION

The period of the COVID-19 pandemic and related restrictions, as well as the conflict in Ukraine, have highlighted the fragility of food chains and international markets (UN, 2022; FAO et al, 2022). They were already affected by conflict, climate change and large price fluctuations, and now the war in Ukraine is intensifying the threat to food security. The worst affected areas are those already facing high levels of poverty and vulnerability (UN, 2022). Smallholder farmers, who are the backbone of agriculture, are often also the most vulnerable group in the rural area and food system (UN, 2022).

FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) statistics present the state of food security and nutrition by 2021. However, the conflict in Ukraine has multiple implications for trade, production channels and price dynamics, and the effects are not quantified. What is certain is that the implications of this conflict represents an additional challenge to achieving Sustainable Development Goal 2 (SDG 2.1 – Eradicate hunger and ensure access to adequate food for all; SDG 2.2 – Eradicate all forms of malnutrition) (FAO et al, 2022).

Romania, like many other countries, faces a number of food-related challenges, including rising food prices, food insecurity, accentuated by the COVID-19 pandemic and the ongoing conflict in Ukraine. According to the 2022 SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) Report, 1.7 million people in Romania could not afford a healthy diet in 2020, a number that is still rising compared to 2019 and 2018, and 2.3 million in 2017. The prevalence of food insecurity in Romania averaging around 15% in 2019-2021 (FAO, 2022, FAOSTAT).

Furthermore, we take into account the European Parliament's motion for a resolution on addressing food security in developing countries (2021/2208(INI)) which motivates, among others, the Emergency Action Plan for Food Security; the Sustainable Development Goals; the 2030 Agenda Goals; the European Green Pact and the Farm to Food Strategy; and the FAO International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (Kempa, 2022). More specifically, it takes into account the severity and scale of food crises aggravated after 2020 by conflicts, economic shocks and extreme weather events; the destabilisation of already fragile agricultural markets as a result of the pandemic and conflict in Ukraine; the loss of about 75% of plant genetic diversity and large-scale genetic erosion; the need to strengthen biodiversity resilience and support ecosystem integrity, with benefits for livelihoods, human health and well-being, and food supply; along with the importance of local agricultural traditions, prioritising local food production, strengthening family farming systems, and increasing local food consumption (Kempa, 2022).

In this context, the promotion and use of landraces responds to the Sustainable Development Goals, in particular Goal 2, sub-points: 2.4 – Ensuring sustainable food production systems and sustainable agricultural practices by 2030; 2.5 Maintain the genetic diversity of seeds, cultivated plants, livestock, domesticated animals and wild relatives through conservation methods; and promote access the benefits arising from the use of genetic resources, associated traditional knowledge, and their fair and equitable sharing, as internationally agreed; 2.A Increase investment, including through enhanced international cooperation, in rural infrastructure, agricultural research and extension services, technology development and plant and animal gene banks to increase agricultural productive capacity in developing countries (FAO et al., 2022).

Providing food for today's population of more than 8,1 billion, and the more than 8,5 billion projected for 2030, requires a 70% increase in food production in developing countries (compared to 1995–1997), of which 80% should be plant-based. Plant breeding has an important contribution to make in this respect, by creating new varieties and high-performance hybrids. In the context of climate change, they must also be resistant to environmental stress and disease and pest attack (Cristea, 2020). Landraces and wild varieties are an essential genetic source in the creation of these new varieties and hybrids. The sustainable use of genetic resources is now recognised as the most effective way to ensure food security (Cristea, 2020).

With this paper we want to highlight the need for conservation and use of local landraces as plant genetic resources, part of the national and international heritage,

important for the development of new varieties and hybrids, for the sustainable development of the mountain area and in response to various Strategic Development Goals, especially those related to climate change, food security and biodiversity conservation. Also, in the last part, we present a case study with positive results in terms of increasing the subculture interval of *in vitro* plantlets, as part of the efforts in improving *in vitro* conservation methods. Although some aspects have been treated separately in the literature, to the best of our knowledge, the results presented below have not been the subject of a scientific article.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

a. Bibliographic study

A part of our work is represented by the bibliographical study, where we processed data from various national and international databases on: crop landraces cultivated in the mountain area of Romania, the difficulties faced by mountain communities in Romania, the advantages and disadvantages of cultivating crop landraces, current ways of promoting crop landraces, respectively methods of their conservation.

b. *In vitro* cultivation

For the preservation of different types of phytoinocultures belonging to the species *Solanum tuberosum* and *Beta vulgaris*, respectively, the efficiency of various culture media (Table 1) of complex compositions was tested, in order to determine their effectiveness in supporting slow growth of these and vitroplants. The measure was combined with a decrease in temperature in the preservation chamber (Gopal and Chauhan, 2010; Koc et al., 2014). The vitroecological regime should be below the optimal values for *in vitro* culture of the species under study, but ensure that their regenerative capacity is maintained. For this purpose, specific *in vitro* culture methods and techniques were used. To the basic medium used in the culture of phytoinocultures, Murashige-Skoog (Murashige and Skoog, 1962), different growth agents were added according to Table 1.

Furthermore, research trips were carried out in the mountainous area of Romania to identify and collect plant genetic resources, represented by crop landraces cultivated *in situ* in traditional households.

Table 1. Culture media used at the Suceava Gene Bank for the preservation of phytoinocula. Murashige-Skoog recipe for phytoinoculum culture media with different growth agents

Mineral components	Quantity (mg/l)	Organic components	Quantity (mg/l)			
			I	II	III	IV
Medium	I, II, III, IV	Medium	I	II	III	IV
NH ₄ NO ₃	825	m-Inositol	100,00			
KNO ₃	950	Thiamine HCl	0,20			
CaCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	330	Pyridoxine HCl	0,20			
MgSO ₄ 7 H ₂ O	185	Nicotinic acid	0,20			
K H ₂ PO ₄	85	Glycine	0,20			
KI	0,42	ANA	0,01			

Mineral components	Quantity (mg/l)	Organic components	Quantity (mg/l)			
			I	II	III	IV
Medium	I,II,III,IV	Medium				
H ₃ BO ₃	3,1	Kinetin	0,01			
MnSO ₄ H ₂ O	11,1	Benziladenine	0,01			
ZnSO ₄ 7 H ₂ O	4,3					
Na ₂ MO O ₄ 2H ₂ O	0,13	Daminozide (B 9)	-	30	-	-
CuSO ₄ 5 H ₂ O	0,013	Manitol (g/l)	30	-	40	-
CoCl ₂ 6H ₂ O	0,013	Sorbitol (g/l)	-	-		40
FeSO ₄ 7 H ₂ O	27,80	Saccharose (g/l)	20			
Na ₂ EDTA 2H ₂ O	37,30	Agar-agar (g/l)	7,2			

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Crop landraces – a component of promoting sustainable and resilient development in mountain areas

Landraces refer to varieties of food plants and crops that have been cultivated in a particular region or area over many generations so that they have evolved and adapted to local environmental, climate and soil conditions and are often better adapted to local growing conditions than non-local varieties (Murariu and Murariu, 2008; Cristea, 2020).

They often have unique flavours, textures and nutritional profiles specific to the region. They are more resistant to pests and diseases prevalent in the area, which can reduce the need for pesticides and other chemicals (Murariu and Murariu, 2008; Rotar et al., 2014). They can help support local food systems and economies. Farmers who grow these crops can sell them in local markets, towards restaurants and in other forms of marketing (local products and dishes), which can help boost the local economy and promote sustainable farming practices. Their conservation and promotion is important for maintaining biodiversity, supporting local food systems and promoting sustainable agricultural practices (Cachiță and Sand, 2011). The use of landraces in mountain areas can be an important part of promoting sustainable and resilient development in these regions.

Crop landraces have multiple uses. They serve as sources of individual characters for certain breeding programmes, as polygenic sources in pre-breeding activities, as local germplasm underlying the development of local varieties, or directly through multiplication and seed distribution at farm level. Among the reasons for the low use of plant genetic resources are a lack of characterisation and evaluation data, of documentation and circulation of information, of appropriate legislation, and poor collaboration between gene banks and germplasm users. The high use of plant genetic resources is constrained by the genetic non-uniformity of landraces, which hampers pre-breeding work in the breeding field. There are also constraints from the flawed bureaucratic regime in the distribution of seeds nationally and internationally, and the insufficient allocation of funds for basic and applied agricultural research (Străjeru et al., 2001).

b. Main challenges facing mountain communities in Romania

Among the main challenges facing mountain communities in Romania are:

1. **Climate change:** Mountain areas are particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, including changes in temperature, precipitation and extreme weather events. These changes can have a significant impact on agricultural production and food security.
2. **Soil degradation:** Many mountain soils are thin and fragile, making them vulnerable to erosion, nutrient depletion and other forms of degradation. This can make it difficult to grow crops and limit the productivity of farming systems.
3. **Limited access to markets:** Mountain communities often face limited access to markets, which can make it difficult to sell their products and generate income. This can make it difficult for farmers to invest in their farms and improve their productivity.
4. **Migration and population decline:** Many mountain communities are facing population decline as young people migrate to towns in search of jobs and opportunities. This leads to a loss of traditional knowledge and skills, as well as a decrease in the number of people available to work on farms.

In this context, the promotion and use of landraces can be a response to some of these challenges by improving the productivity and resilience of farming systems, enhancing food security, promoting economic development and supporting sustainability in mountain areas. This is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the European Parliament's motion for a resolution on addressing food security in developing countries.

c. Promoting the use of landraces

Promoting the use of landraces in mountain areas can present both challenges and opportunities. Challenges include:

1. **Limited availability:** Many landraces have disappeared or are threatened due to changes in agricultural practices and the influence of global markets. This can make access to landraces difficult.
2. **Lack of knowledge:** Many farmers may not be aware of the benefits of landraces or how to grow them effectively.
3. **Low yields:** Some landraces may have lower yields or be less productive than non-local varieties, making them less attractive to farmers.
4. **Market access:** Market opportunities are often limited for products grown from landraces, making it difficult for farmers to make a living from these crops.

There are, however, institutions that promote and support the use of local populations by providing access to seeds, cultivation guides and other resources:

- European project INCREASE – <https://www.pulsesincrease.eu/> A project for the conservation, management and research of genetic resources (partners – Suceava Gene Bank, Bacău legume research station, FAO, etc.);
- Suceava Gene Bank – https://svgenebank.ro/projects_ro.asp;
- SAVE Foundation – <https://save-foundation.net/home-en/> Pan-European organisation for the protection and assurance of local landraces and animal breeds; network of organisations;
- Carpathian Network for Agrobiodiversity <http://agrobiodiversity.net/carpathiannet/> (part of the SAVE network);

- Farmer's Pride Project <http://www.farmerspride.eu/> A tool for those who maintain local varieties or those who are considering growing local varieties to diversify their farming system. Includes examples of *in situ* management practices and local variety value addition, e.g. marketing options, for different crops and socio-cultural, environmental and economic contexts. Under this project, actions have also been undertaken in Romania to conserve local populations of spruce and garlic;
- ECP/GR <https://www.ecpgr.cgiar.org/> – European cooperation programme for plant genetic resources.

Opportunities and benefits associated with landraces include:

- Adaptability: they are more resistant to climate change, diseases and pests, and are less likely to fail in times of drought or other stressors compared to non-local varieties.
- Genetic diversity: they often have a high level of genetic diversity, which is a valuable source of genetic material for crop improvement and breeding programmes.
- Biodiversity conservation: they are unique to mountain areas and may be at risk of extinction due to factors such as habitat loss and climate change.
- Environmental sustainability: by promoting the use of landraces, farmers can help maintain the diversity of local ecosystems, conserve genetic resources and reduce the use of synthetic inputs such as pesticides and fertilisers.
- Nutritional value: can provide nutritional benefits not available in modern crops, some plants are rich in certain vitamins or minerals, or have unique flavours that can be showcased in local products and dishes.
- Cultural heritage: local populations have been cultivated for generations and are an important part of the cultural heritage of mountain communities. By promoting the use of these plants, farmers can help preserve traditional knowledge and practices and strengthen local identities.
- Economic benefits: can provide economic benefits to farmers by reducing their dependence on costly inputs and improving the marketing of their products.

Producing new cultivars means making better use of genetic diversity. As pressure on the mountain increases, there is a need to achieve stable yields with decreasing use of chemicals and irrigation (Străjeru et al., 2001).

A long-term strategy should include the use of underused and hitherto unused species; supporting farmers in the use of landraces and other conserved PGR (plant genetic resources) in gene banks; promoting the use of local populations in breeding programmes; increasing the training capacity of staff working in breeding; increasing collaboration between breeders and gene banks; evaluating all conserved germplasm; and developing pre-breeding activities through comprehensive long-term programmes (Străjeru et al., 2001).

d. Approaches to conserving landraces

There are three main ways to conserve landraces. The first is *in situ*, at the level of farms and households in the mountain area; the second is *ex situ*, in gene banks and other institutions and collections; and the third is in the form of *in vitro* cultures (Cachiță and Sand, 2011; Cristea, 2020). Each of these is discussed below, in the context of the conservation of landraces in the Romanian mountain area, and our personal contribution to their conservation.

e. *In situ* conservation of landraces on farms and households in mountain areas of Romania

A large number of landraces are still preserved in Bucovina, Maramures and the Apuseni Mountains (Simeonovska et al., 2013) and are an essential part of peasant households, where traditional agriculture has been preserved and is part of the local identity (Figure 1). The way local landraces and animal breeds are processed and used often involves traditional methods and practices that have been preserved over time as a way of life for mountain people. Today, these are an attractive aspect of agro-tourism, which, together with traditional products, from food to fabrics and other handicrafts, contribute to their preservation, local identity, and bring economic benefits through marketing (Figure 2).

Fig. 1. Peasant households in the harvesting area of local populations. Aspects regarding cultivation conditions for crop landraces conditions in mountain area.

Source: original photo

Fig. 2. Marketing of traditional products obtained in peasant households. Products made with plant resources obtained from crop landraces of *Triticum* sp. as well as other vegetable and fruit species.

Source: original photo

Romania has a rich agricultural tradition and numerous crop landraces, such as:

- Potatoes: There are many local varieties that are well adapted to growing conditions in mountainous areas. Potato, is considered among the top 4 crops, after wheat, rice and maize, whose genetic production potential can be decisive for ensuring human existence (Cristea, 2020).
- Beans: Beans are another important crop in Romania and there are many local varieties that are appreciated for their taste and nutritional value. *Phaseolus coccineus*, almost entirely extinct, is resistant to low temperatures. More than 300 local populations of *Phaseolus vulgaris* are still preserved in the north of the country, especially in Bucovina (Străjeru, 2018).
- Tomatoes: Although tomatoes are not traditionally associated with mountain farming in Romania, there are many local varieties that can be grown successfully in these areas. Certified varieties 'Cassiana' and 'Danamari', derived from local populations in Sălaj and Alba, show resistance to *Phytophthora infestans* infection, and are suitable for organic cultivation (Străjeru, 2018).
- Maize: Maize is an important crop in many parts of Romania, including mountainous areas. Varieties resistant to low temperatures include Ilva mica 45, Pojorâta 20, Lunca Ilvei 3 (Murariu and Murariu, 2008). Maize, the world's third most important crop in terms of area, has introgression with teosites (*Euchlaena*), several breeds and local populations as its genetic basis for breeding (Cristea, 2020).

Numerous landraces in Romania can be found in the Catalogue of Legume Species (Străjeru, 2018), made available by the Suceava Gene Bank. The origin of these local populations is often in the mountainous area, as shown by the data on harvesting locations included in the catalogue.

Wheat is a major crop worldwide in terms of cultivated area, for which there are four independent wild gene sources: tetraploid *T. dicoccoides*, and for durum wheat – wild einkorn *T. boeoticum*, *Aegilops spaldoides*, and diploid *A. squarosa*. *A. ventricosa* and some wild *Agropyron* species are of interest for resistance to some diseases and pests (Cristea, 2020).

In Romania, in the Apuseni Mountains (Almaşul Mare, Alba county), cultures of einkorn wheat (*T. monococcum* ssp. *monococcum*) have been found, derived from wild einkorn wheat – *T. monococcum* ssp. *boeoticum* (Cristea, 2020). From such a field, samples were collected by Turcuş and collaborators in 2002 and sent to the Suceava Gene Bank and to the Gene Bank of Tápíószele – Hungary, respectively.

Einkorn wheat is resistant to low temperatures, drought, scorching, adapted to poor soil conditions and harsh climate characteristic of mountain areas (Cristea, 2020). Cultivated since the time of Dacia, it is preserved in Romania today in the Centre and North-West of the country, having a good production in conditions where other cereals would not resist as well (clay soils, poor shale substrate, low use of organic fertilisers) (Turcuş, 2007).

In recent years, there has been renewed interest in *T. monococcum* and other ancient grains because of their health benefits and unique flavours. Einkorn wheat is an example of important local wheat population in Romania, and its cultivation and consumption are part of the country's rich agricultural heritage.

By promoting the use of these and other local plant populations in mountain areas, farmers can help promote sustainable and resilient agriculture better adapted to local conditions, improve food security and promote economic development in these regions.

f. *Ex situ* conservation of landraces in gene banks

An important part of conserving plant genetic resources is data management. This is done through databases. They can facilitate collaboration between institutes and beneficiaries of germplasm collections (breeders, gene banks, agricultural education institutions, etc.) as well as international collaboration. The success of such databases depends on the quality of the information provided, which must comply with international standards in the field, allow free access to information, be easy to use, and provide facilities for searching and analysing specific information (Străjeru et al., 2001). In Romania, a quality database is provided by BRGV Suceava, and at the international level, the EURISCO online database, a European catalogue of plant genetic resources, has been created (https://eurisco.ipk-gatersleben.de/apex/eurisco_ws/r/eurisco/home).

The data are grouped according to type and informatics criteria in .dbf files, between which relationships are established through common fields called access numbers or codes, which facilitate the use of the database. An essential part of the database is the Passport with descriptors established by FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation) and IPGRI (International Plant Genetic Resources Institute). There are two types of descriptors: standardised and valid for all crop plants and descriptors specific to certain plants or categories of plants. The database structure also includes storage data (with specific files for each type of conservation and depending on the type of genetic material conserved), characterisation and evaluation descriptors (available in the form of images and files with specific data for each species evaluated), information on *in situ* conservation, details on pedoclimatic characteristics, information on the management of stored material (number of available seeds, results of viability tests, number of propagations, etc.), herbarium data and other information in the form of codes for countries, Romanian counties and institutions (Străjeru et al., 2001).

Evaluation of morphological characters is carried out in the field or in the laboratory, depending on the species. In the case of maize, this is carried out in the laboratory and the following characteristics are assessed: length of main cob (cm), cob shape, maximum and minimum diameter of main cob (mm), number of rows of grains, number of grains/row, grain colour, covariety (hard, dentate, sugary, starchy), grain length (mm), grain width (mm), weight of grains/cobs (gr), mass of 1000 grains (gr) (Străjeru et al., 2001; IBPGR, 1991).

According to IPGRI, there are 5 categories of descriptors related to plant germplasm, which include passport descriptors, characterisation data, primary assessment, secondary assessment, and information needed for plant germplasm management. Characterisation data and primary evaluation are carried out in genebanks. Secondary evaluation, including for example biochemical descriptors, is carried out by multidisciplinary teams of researchers from other institutions, but the results are still stored in gene bank databases. Biochemical descriptors refer to the main chemical components of the seeds stored in the collections, depending on the species, such as the percentage of protein, fat, starch in maize; lysine and allozyme content in wheat. The latter also allow the detection of possible duplicates in the collections (Străjeru et al., 2001).

Our own results on this evaluation step were obtained in a study that aimed to evaluate morphological and productivity characteristics in local maize and tomato populations (Turcuş et al., 2022). Seed material of local populations of *Zea mays* L. and *Solanum lycopersicum* L. (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.), was collected from Geoagiu Băi (depressional area south-east of the Metaliferous Mountains), and cultivated *ex situ* at Socodor (western

part of the Crișului Alb Plain), to see if changes in phenotypic characters occur under environmental conditions different from those at the collection site. According to the results obtained, *ex situ* cultivation of local plant populations for a short period of time does not influence genotypic and phenotypic characters under new pedoclimatic conditions (Turcuș et al., 2022).

g. *In vitro* conservation

A central activity of the Suceava Gene Bank is the conservation of plant species or genotypes, including local plant populations. This consists of maintaining collections of plant material under controlled environmental conditions that ensure its viability and genetic stability for as long as possible. Three methods are used to achieve this: maintaining plants in field collections, storing seeds, and preserving finoinocula.

In vitro culture techniques are of increasing interest, both for the propagation and conservation of germplasm and for the propagation of plant material at a higher rate of efficiency than conventional methods. Within the Gene Bank of Suceava, besides the conservation of local varieties of potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), which is the main concern of the specialized laboratory, the bank's collections also include several other plant species, including: *Beta vulgaris* L., *Triticum aestivum* L., *Zea mays* L. These phytovitrocultures serve as experimental models in the studies that are carried out in the bank, with the aim of developing techniques for the vitropreservation of plant genetic resources, with an increase in the subculture interval of phytoinocula.

h. Study case. *In vitro* conservation of potato and beetroot landraces (Cachiță-Cosma și Constantinovici, 2008)

The following are the results of experiments aimed at monitoring the evolution of phytoinocula under the conditions of increasing the culture interval of the vitroculture and extending the storage period. At the same time, the aim was to ensure their viability and vitality, especially in genotypes with a higher sensitivity to the stressful conditions of their conservation regime.

In potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), phytoinocula stored in the bank underwent successive cycles of slow-growth preservation for 16 to 18 months, followed for a further 6 to 8 months by subcultivation of the phytoinocula on fresh media, while regeneration of the phytoinocula with microtubules took place (Cachiță-Cosma și Constantinovici, 2008). For each preservation cycle, uninodal cuttings from shoots regenerated at the vitroculture level in the micro-multiplication phase were replanted on two types of culture media, which differed in the retarding agent they contained (Table 1). Genetic material from more than 80 local potato varieties was subcultured on culture media I and II (Table 1), in which the retarding agents were mannitol at a dose of 30 g/l and daminozide at a concentration of 30 mg/l, respectively. In one batch of potato vitrocultures, the initial preservation period was extended to 24–28 months from the operation of subculture of the cuttings on media III and IV, in which the retarding agents were mannitol (40 g/l) and sorbitol (40 g/l), respectively. The appearance of the vitrocultures – 28 months after the subculture operation – revealed differences in their growth type, at the level of minitubers, a regeneration of numerous shoots and pods was observed (Figure 3 A-E).

Fig. 3. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) (SBGB-15032) *in vitro* slow-growing cultures, inoculated on media III and IV, with the addition of mannitol (A) and sorbitol (B), respectively; C-E – details on the appearance of the inoculums 28 months after subculturing for preservation purposes

Source: original photo

Fig. 4. Sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) propagules rooted in the first period of preservation (A and B), grown on medium II (with daminosidase type II); respectively regeneration of flowering minisets (C and D), after 12 months of preservation under slow growth conditions on the same type of medium with daminosidase.

Source: original photo

In the course of the conservation experiments of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* var. *saccharifera*) phytoinocula, the biological material used in micropropagation consisted of a diploid, monogerm, fertile source (2xmmF). Micromultiplication of this species was carried out using propagules isolated from leaflet clumps regenerated from another propagule in a vitroculture prior to the conservation experiment, each consisting of a basal portion on which 5–9 leaflets, 1.5–3 cm long, were embedded. Rhizogenesis in sugar beet *in vitro* is difficult and highly variable in terms of its incidence and intensity, a fact that is also stated in the literature. On medium II, with daminozide (30 mg/l), during the preservation period, and under reduced ambient temperatures from 22°C to 6–12°C, beet propagules generated well-conformed roots (Figure 4 A and B). After the first 12 months of slow growth, the colour of the beet leaves turned slightly yellowish (Figure 4 C and D), with flowering stems regenerating from the propagules. Measures to attenuate the growth rate of beetroot rootstocks led to a reduction in the number of regenerated leaflets in the propagules used to initiate vitrocultures for slow-growing storage, thus ensuring that the interval between propagation was prolonged and the vitality of the propagules was maintained on the same culture medium.

CONCLUSION

Local plant varieties can help support sustainable and resilient development in mountain areas by providing farmers with crops that are adapted to local growing conditions, resistant to environmental changes, pests and diseases, and culturally and economically valuable. However, the challenges and opportunities associated with these crops need to be addressed. Education and training of the population/farmers, access to markets and collaboration between farmers and researchers are also important. The use of these local plant varieties can be an asset for producing specific food products that improve agro-tourism in these areas.

Due to the large number of local populations in Romania, exchanges of plant germplasm with specialized companies can be improved in order to obtain hybrids or varieties, which would generate economic development in the mountain community.

Local landraces are the most important gene resources that contribute to new hybrids in crop plants in the future. They represent an invaluable resource for mountain areas, a material heritage of the people of these areas, and must be protected both *in situ* and *ex situ*.

AUTHOR(S) CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, V.T. and D.C.C.; Data curation, V.T., D.C.C., P.A., V.B.B. and G.G.A.; Formal analysis, V.T., D.C.C., G.A.A. and V.B.B.; Funding acquisition, V.T. and D.C.C.; Investigation, V.T., D.C.C. and V.B.B.; Methodology, V.T., D.C.C., P.A., V.B.B. and G.G.A.; Project administration, V.T. and D.C.C.; Resources, V.T. and D.C.C.; Software, P.A., and V.B.B.; Supervision, V.T., D.C.C. and G.G.A.; Validation, V.T., D.C.C. and G.G.A.; Visualization, P.A. and V.B.B.; Roles/Writing – original draft, V.T., D.C.C., P.A., V.B.B. and G.G.A.; and Writing – review & editing, V.T. and V.B.B.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the results of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [V.T.].

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